

INTERCHARACTER ASSOCIATION AND PATH COEFFICIENT STUDIES OF SEGREGATING BACKCROSSED GENERATION (BC₁F₃) IN RICE (*Oryza sativa* L.)*H. P. Vadodariya¹, R. K. Patel², D. V. Makwana³, H. D. Kundaria⁴ and G. D. Vadodariya⁵^{1,2}Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, NMCA, NAU, Navsari*Corresponding author's email: himanivadodariya@gmail.com

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Abstract

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a major and staple food, which feeds more than half of the population of world, majorly in Asian countries, where it has an important role in ensuring food security. In the present study, we delve into the intricate relationships among various agronomic traits in rice cultivation, employing correlation and path analysis methodologies to unveil the underlying factors influencing growth and yield. An experimental material consisted of 221 BC₁F₃ plants, which were developed from a cross between Gurjari (recurrent parent) and Tetep (Donor parent). The correlation studies on ten yield and its attributing characters indicated that grain yield per plant was significantly and positively correlated with plant height, productive tillers per plant, panicle length, grains per panicle, straw yield per plant, harvest index and 100 grain weight. The path co-efficient analysis had shown higher positive direct effect on grain yield per plant by productive tillers per plant followed by harvest index, days to flowering, grains per panicle, and straw yield per plant, which may provide expected advance during the selection for yield of the grain.

Key words - Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.), cultivation, employing correlation and path analysis methodologies.

Introduction

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a major and staple food, which feeds more than half of the population of world, where it is a dietary mainstay. Rice, being a vital cereal crop, holds paramount importance in global food security (Khush, 2005). Because rice plays such an important role in providing food security, there is a growing need to improve production, quality, and resilience in the face of changing environmental circumstances. In the pursuit of optimizing rice production, researchers have turned to advanced statistical tools to unravel the intricate relationships among various agronomic traits. Among these tools, correlation and path analysis emerge as powerful techniques, offering insights into the nature and strength of associations between different variables.

Understanding the intricate relationships between various agronomic traits in rice is fundamental for maximizing yield and quality parameters (Yoshida et al., 2012). Correlation analysis serves as an initial step in unveiling potential associations among these traits, offering insights into their interdependence and potential implications (Gomez & Gomez, 1984). However, correlation alone cannot elucidate the underlying causal relationships among traits, necessitating the utilization of path analysis (Wright, 1921). Path analysis goes beyond correlation by unraveling direct and indirect effects, thereby constructing a comprehensive framework to discern the primary drivers influencing yield, quality, and other critical traits in rice (Dewey & Lu, 1959).

In this research, we delve into the intricate relationships among various agronomic traits in rice cultivation, employing correlation and path analysis methodologies to unveil the underlying factors influencing growth and yield. So, the present study was conducted to assess the inter character correlation between yield and yield contributing various traits among 221 segregants in BC₁F₃ generation of Gurjari × Tetep.

Materials and Method**Experimental location and generation of material**

An experimental material consisted of 221 BC₁F₃ plants, which were developed from a cross between Gurjari (recurrent parent) and Tetep (Donor parent). A non-replicated experiment block of 221 BC₁F₃s were raised along with parents and check variety GR-17(Sardar) at Main Rice Research Station (MRRS), Navsari Agricultural University, Navsari in Summer, 2023. Observations were taken from the parents, check and individual plant of segregating BC₁F₃s population for the ten quantitative parameters viz., days to flowering, days to maturity, plant height (cm), productive tillers per plant, panicle length (cm), 100 grain weight (g), grains per panicle, straw yield per plant (g), harvest index (%) and grain yield per plant (g).

Statistical Analysis

Weber and Moorthy (1952) provided the formula, which were used for calculating simple correlations in a present study. Moreover,

formulas for path analysis given by Wright (1921) and Dewey and Lu (1959) was used in this study for partitioning the genotypic correlation between different variables/characters with grain yield into direct and indirect effects of that respective variables on the grain yield. Heatmap representing intercharacter correlation was prepared by using R software (Fig. 1).

Result and Discussion**Correlation coefficient analysis**

Data depicted in Table 1 showed that days to flowering showed positive and highly significant correlation with days to maturity (0.983), plant height (0.284) and straw yield per plant (0.259). Days to maturity rendered positive and highly significant correlation with plant height (0.263) and straw yield per plant (0.234) and positive significant correlation with panicle length (0.136). The data on plant height showed that it was positive and significantly associated with productive tillers per plant (0.237), panicle length (0.208), straw yield per plant (0.538) and grain yield per plant (-0.221). Productive tillers per plant were positively and significantly associated with panicle length (0.193), straw yield per plant (0.414) grain yield per plant (0.691) and 100 grain weight (0.137), while it was negative and significantly associated with harvest index (-0.007). Additionally, it showed positive and non-significant association with grains per panicle (0.080).

Panicle length was positively and highly significantly associated with grains per panicle (0.229), straw yield per plant (0.229) and grain yield per plant (0.251). The correlation between 100 grain weight and harvest index (0.306) was positive and highly significant. Grains per panicle were positively and highly significantly associated with harvest index (0.240) and grain yield per plant (0.521).

Data on grain yield per plant showed positive and highly significant correlation with plant height (0.221), productive tillers per plant (0.691), panicle length (0.251), grains per panicle (0.521), straw yield per plant (0.394) and harvest index (0.240) and positive significant association with 100 grain weight (0.167). However, it remains negative and highly significant with days to flowering (0.170) and days to maturity (-0.187). The findings were akin to the work of Immanuel et al. (2011), Beerelli et al. (2021), Bhargava et al. (2022), Prajapati et al. (2022) and Prathiksha et al. (2022). However, correlation with grain yield per plant remains negative and highly significant for days to flowering (-0.170) and days to maturity (-0.187) and it is supported by Kahani and Hittalmani (2015), Hemant et al. (2018) and Renuprasath et al. (2023).

In the present investigation, it has been found that a significant and desired directional inherent and observable correlation was registered between grain yield and all characters under investigation except days to 50 per cent flowering and days to maturity. This showed that all traits have inherent relationship with grain yield, which also depicted

their importance in grain yield enhancement and can be done by improving those characters.

Path analysis

Data shown in Table 2 and Fig 2 depicted that days to flowering exhibited significant and negative correlation with grain yield per plant (-0.170*). The direct effect of days to flowering on grain yield per plant was recorded and found positive (0.358). Days to maturity showed significant and negative correlation with grain yield per plant (-0.187**). Plant height showed a low positive direct effect (0.131) on grain yield per plant. While it had negligible positive indirect effects via days to flowering (0.102), productive tillers per plant (0.118), panicle length (0.001) and straw yield per plant (0.183). Its positive and highly significant correlation (0.220**) with grain yield per plant was due to the negligible indirect negative effect and low positive indirect effect.

Productive tillers per plant showed a positive direct effect (0.499) on grain yield per plant. It also showed negligible positive indirect effects via days to maturity (0.055), plant height (0.030), panicle length (0.001), 100 grain weight (0.007), grains per panicle (0.028) and straw yield per plant (0.141). Its positive and highly significant association (0.691**) with grain yield per plant was due to high positive direct and negligible indirect effects. Panicle length exhibited a low positive direct effect (0.004) on grain yield per plant. Additionally, high positive direct and negligible indirect effects might be a cause of highly significant and positive correlation with grain yield per plant (-0.251**).

100 grain weight showed significant and positive correlation with grain yield per plant (0.167*). The direct effect of 100 grain weight on grain yield per plant was recorded and found positive (0.050). This

trait had positive indirect effect *via* days to maturity (0.083), productive tillers per plant (0.068) and harvest index (0.136).

Grains per panicle revealed positive and highly significant association with grain yield per plant (0.521**). It had positive direct effect on grain yield per plant (0.349). Straw yield per plant showed a positive direct effect (0.341) on grain yield per plant. Additionally, it exhibited positive and highly significant correlation (0.394**) with grain yield per plant.

In the present experiment, it has been revealed that the highest positive and direct influence on grain yield per plant was exerted by productive tillers per plant followed by harvest index, days to flowering, grains per panicle, and straw yield per plant (Table 2). Thus, direct selection for this trait will surely be rewarding for improving grain yield per plant. Similar results were found by Immanuel *et al.* (2011), Suresh *et al.* (2014), Sala and Shanthi (2016), Vaibhav *et al.* (2019), Bhargava *et al.* (2022), Nihad *et al.* (2022) and Renuprasath *et al.* (2023). Days to maturity exhibited negative direct effect on grain yield per plant, but it has indirect positive influence *via* days to flowering, plant height, panicle length and harvest index. Similar results were observed by Immanuel *et al.* (2011). Despite negative direct effect, it showed positive correlation coefficient with grain yield per plant, which explained indirect effects as a cause of the correlation. In such conditions, it is preferable to consider other factors simultaneously.

Present investigation showed 0.20 residual effect, which indicated that the characters which were selected in this study contributed 80 % to the yield. So, inclusion of more characters might increase accountable variation in future. Kahani and hittalmani (2015), Sala and Shanthi (2016), Bhargava *et al.* (2022) were also reported the same.

Table 1: Inter-character correlation in BC₁F₃ population

	DF	DM	PH	PTP	PL	100GW	GP	SYP	HI	GYP
DF	1.000									
DM	0.983**	1.000								
PH	0.284**	0.263**	1.000							
PTP	-0.189**	-0.178**	0.237**	1.000						
PL	0.130 ^{NS}	0.136*	0.208**	0.193**	1.000					
100GW	-0.297**	-0.269**	-0.167*	0.137*	-0.079 ^{NS}	1.000				
GP	-0.049 ^{NS}	-0.075 ^{NS}	-0.061 ^{NS}	0.080 ^{NS}	0.229**	-0.034 ^{NS}	1.000			
SYP	0.259**	0.234**	0.538**	0.414**	0.229**	-0.087 ^{NS}	0.086 ^{NS}	1.000		
HI	-0.505**	-0.489**	-0.459**	-0.007 ^{NS}	-0.077 ^{NS}	0.306**	0.240**	-0.611**	1.000	
GYP	-0.170*	-0.187**	0.221**	0.691**	0.251**	0.167*	0.521**	0.394**	0.240**	1.000

Table 2: Direct and indirect effects of ten characters on grain yield in BC₁F₃ population

	DF	DM	PH	PTP	PL	100GW	GP	SYP	HI
DF	0.358	0.352	0.102	-0.067	0.046	-0.106	-0.017	0.092	-0.180
DM	-0.304	-0.309	-0.081	0.055	-0.041	0.083	0.023	-0.072	0.151
PH	0.037	0.034	0.131	0.030	0.027	-0.021	-0.008	0.070	-0.060
PTP	-0.094	-0.088	0.118	0.499	0.096	0.068	0.040	0.206	-0.003
PL	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.001	0.004	0.000	0.001	0.001	0.000
100GW	-0.015	-0.013	-0.008	0.007	-0.004	0.050	-0.002	-0.004	0.015
GP	-0.017	-0.026	-0.021	0.028	0.079	-0.011	0.349	0.030	0.084
SYP	0.088	0.080	0.183	0.141	0.077	-0.030	0.029	0.341	-0.208
HI	-0.224	-0.216	-0.203	-0.003	-0.033	0.136	0.106	-0.270	0.443
GYP	-0.170*	-0.187**	0.220**	0.691**	0.251**	0.167*	0.521**	0.394**	0.240**

DF : Days to flowering

DM : Days to maturity

PH : Plant height (cm)

PTP : Productive tillers per plant

PL : Panicle length (cm)

100 GW

GP : Grains per panicle

SYP : Straw yield per plant (g)

HI : Harvest index (%)

GYP : Grain yield per plant (g)

* and **, significant at 5 % and 1 % levels of probability, respectively ($P \leq 0.05$ * and $P \leq 0.01$ **) Residual = 0.20 and bold diagonal figures are the direct effect

Conclusion

In the present experiment, it can be concluded that grain yield per plant showed positive and highly significant correlation with plant height, productive tillers per plant, panicle length, grains per panicle, straw yield per plant and harvest index and positive significant association with 100 grain weight. Since, these character associations are in the desirable direction, selection practiced for the improvement in those characters will automatically result in the improvement of yield. Path coefficient analysis indicates higher positive direct effect on grain yield per plant by productive tillers per plant followed by

harvest index, days to flowering, grains per panicle, and straw yield per plant, which may provide expected advance during selection for grain yield.

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Figure 1: Heat map representing inter character correlation in BC₁F₃ population

Figure 2: Simple path diagram for grain yield imparted by the component variable

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